

CONTACT ANGLE MEASUREMENT FOR SURFACE WETTABILITY ANALYSIS USING IMAGE PROCESSING

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ABSTRACT

The proposed research work introduces a system that enables the measurement of surface wettability using image processing and a static sessile drop method to calculate contact angle at a very low cost. The system is composed of a single-board computer, a motorized liquid dispensing module, and a digital camera, all integrated through a custom graphical user interface. Established computer vision techniques are employed to process sessile-drop images to extract droplet and substrate baseline boundaries, and then contact angle is calculated at both triple-contact point and given a manual correction tool to cover for the low contrast or difficult image conditions. The system was tested on five liquid substrate pairs, among them water on stainless steel (70.18°) and on thermoplastic polyurethane (68.18°). The values measured agree with values in the literature and the small mean difference between the left and the right angles, assures the measurement flow consistency.

KEYWORDS

Contact angle, Surface wettability, sessile drop, image processing, low-cost instrumentation.

1. INTRODUCTION

Surface wettability is an intrinsic material property determining the performance of coatings, biomedical devices, microfluidics, printing, and a multitude of industrial processes. The contact angle, that a liquid droplet makes at the solid surface in the presence of a gas along the line where a liquid-gas interface meets a solid surface, is the most popular quantifiable indicator of wettability [17]. Conventionally, surfaces are considered hydrophilic when water contact angle with the surface is less than 90° and hydrophobic when it is more than 90° .

Commercial instrumentation for contact angle measurements provides a higher level of accuracy and precision but is usually beyond the reach of teaching laboratories, small research groups, or institutions in developing countries because of its price and sophistication in operation. This paper reports on a cheap yet accurate option based on using off-the-shelf components and opensource software to make measurements that are reliable and consistent with those from high-end equipment.

2. LITERATURE REVIEW

Contact angle measurement has been researched for more than a century, ever since the basic thermodynamic formulations were developed by Young [17]. Current methods of measurement can be divided into three major groups: optical analysis of sessile drops, Wilhelmy plate tensiometry and capillary rise methods. The sessile drop method is the most popular one mainly because of its simplicity, non-destructive nature, and ease of visual interpretation. Several open-source projects have successfully democratized contact angle measurements. An ImageJ plug-in for axisymmetric drop shape analysis (ADSA) [9] was introduced by Stalder et al. [1] report

open implementations based on Python and [6], [3] on smartphone technology. These previous works are generally concerned with the analysis stage per se and not with processing. The platform also described here incorporates computerized droplet dispensing (motorized droplet dispensing) in the same application, allowing a complete measurement process.

3. THEORETICAL BACKGROUND

In the case of a liquid droplet on a solid surface in equilibrium with a gas phase, the contact angle θ at the three-phase line, which is a measure of the balance of the interfacial tensions [17], is given by Young's equation. As shown in Figure 1, strong wetting is associated with a small θ and a large θ with weak wetting. In the static sessile drop technique, a tiny droplet is placed on a flat surface and viewed from the side.

Figure 1. Representation of Contact Angle

The contact angle is measured as the angle between the substrate and the tangents to the droplet at the left and right triple contact points, and the mean value of these two contact angles is also reported. The difference between the two is used as a measure of droplet symmetry and repeatability of measurements.

Reliable sessile drop measurement thus relies on accurate droplet boundary and substrate baseline detection, in addition to a numerically stable estimation of the droplet surface tangent at the contact line.

4. SYSTEM ARCHITECTURE

The system includes four functional subsystems: an imaging subsystem, a motorized dispensing subsystem, a controller, and a graphical user interface. The design is depicted in Figure 2.

Figure 1. System Architecture

A. Hardware Building Blocks

The controller is a Raspberry Pi 4 single board computer. A stepper-motor-driven linear actuator pushes the syringe plunger to dispense liquid. Imaging is done using a digital camera over a standard USB Video Class interface. The system is powered by typical low-voltage power supplies.

B. Software Stack

This software is written in Python 3 and leverages open-source libraries such as PyQt6 for the GUI, OpenCV [11] for image processing, and common scientific computing libraries for processing the numeric. The motor control module provides an abstraction over the hardware GPIO and includes a simulation mode allowing the whole application to be executed on a desktop computer without any hardware connected. A high-level schematic of the software structure is shown in Figure 3.

Figure 2. Software Architecture

5. METHODOLOGY

The measurement workflow proceeds through the following stages, illustrated in Figure 4.

Figure 3. Methodology

A. Stage 1: Liquid Dispensing

A controlled deposition of a liquid droplet on the substrate precedes every measurement. The user sets the dispensing parameters, and the stepper motor-driven syringe is controlled to dispense the specified amount of liquid. Support for: forward and reverse motion, with reverse motion employed after dispensing to minimize dripping post-deposition. In addition, the application features an emergency stop procedure and a simulation methodology, wherein

hardware operations are ignored, intended for use during system development and for demonstration.

B. Stage 2: Image Acquisition

Once the droplet is set, an image can be obtained either from the live camera stream or by importing a saved image file. Live capture works in a background thread to keep GUI responsive and the user can pause the feed to pick the frame for analysis.

C. Stage 3: Droplet Detection

Two alternative routes are provided for the detection of the droplet region.

Automatic detection Applies classic computer vision algorithms on the captured image to separate the droplet from the background. The method performs a combination of classic image processing preprocessing with thresholding then morphological processing, and extracts the most likely droplet candidate from all detected candidates.

For low-contrast images or images with complex background or uncommon droplet forms, manual detection is available. An interactive interface (zoomable canvas) allows the user to mark points around the droplet edge, and from these inputs a smooth contour is constructed by the system. Both routes go to the same downstream process.

D. Stage 4: Baseline Detection

The substrate baseline is found by employing conventional edge and line detection techniques within a window of interest at the droplet base. In the manual mode the user can define the baseline by selecting two points along the substrate.

E. Stage 5: Contact point and Angle Computation

The droplet contour intersections with the substrate baseline are also called left and right triple-contact points. From each contact point, the local tangent of the droplet boundary is computed and the angle between this tangent and the baseline is calculated. Both numbers are reported separately and third is reported as the averaged contact angle.

F. Stage 6: Volume Estimation

The volume of the droplet can be calculated assuming rotational symmetry about the z-axis using well-known axisymmetric integration. The result is given in microliters after multiplying by a pixel to millimeter calibration factor from the user.

G. Stage 7: Visualization and Export

The detected contour, baseline, contact points and tangent indicators are plotted on the original image and shown to the user along with the numerical results. The user can download the original image, the annotated overlay, a CSV file containing all the numerical data and a well-structured PDF report.

GRAPHICAL USER INTERFACE:

All of the functionality is accessible from a single application window shown in Figure 5. The interface comprises sample identification, image and camera analysis, results, export, and dispenser controls in separate panels.

Fig. 4. GUI Interface

The viewer can zoom in and out and pan over the droplet and the overlay. Interactive manual marking of the drop outline and baseline on the captured image is supported in a dedicated dialog as shown in Figure 6.

Figure 5. Manual Selection Window

There is a simulation mode that lets you run the full application without any motor hardware attachments, which is great for training and demos.

6. Results and Discussion

The system was verified by measurements of five different liquid–substrate systems, and in all cases the substrates were used as received without any cleaning or pretreatment. All analyses were carried out using the polynomial tangent method in manual detection mode to maintain a uniform contour quality in the different substrates texture.

A. Study A: Water on Different Substrates

Distilled water droplets were deposited on three different substrate materials. The measured contact angles are summarized in Table I and visualized in Figure 7.

Figure 6.A Water on Steel

Figure 7.B Water on Glass

Figure 7.C Water on Foam Board

Table 1. Water on Different Substrates

Substrate	θ_{left} ($^{\circ}$)	θ_{right} ($^{\circ}$)	$\theta_{average}$ ($^{\circ}$)	Volume (μL)
Stainless Steel	68.56	71.80	70.18	22.11
Thermoplastic Polyurethane (TPU)	65.40	70.97	68.18	7.11
Foam Board	59.87	62.61	61.24	34.72

The contact angles are clearly ordered: water has the lowest contact angle on foam board (61.24°), an intermediate value on TPU (68.18°), and the highest on stainless steel (70.18°). All the three substrates are in the hydrophilic regime ($\theta < 90^{\circ}$). This order agrees well with the chemical properties of the substrates: the porous cellulose based, high-energy surface of the foam board encourages wetting, the polar urethane linkages of the TPU are weakly hydrophilic, and the as-received stainless steel commonly has a thin layer of adsorbed organics which is mildly hydrophobic and tends to increase the contact angle relative to clean atomic surfaces.

B. Study B: Multiple Liquid Characterization

To illustrate the versatility of the system to work with liquids with very different optical and physical properties, measurements were performed with three liquids — distilled water, cooking oil, and writing ink. The results are summarized in Table II and visualized in Figure 8.

Figure 7.A Water on Foam Board

Figure 8.B Cooking Oil on Foam Board

Figure 8.C Ink on PVC

Table 2. Contact Angle for different Liquids

Liquid	Substrate	θ_{left} (°)	θ_{right} (°)	$\theta_{average}$ (°)	Volume (μL)
Water	Foam board	59.87	62.61	61.24	34.72
Cooking Oil	Foam board	61.38	64.56	62.997	1.52
Ink	PVC	64.67	67.09	65.88	8.06

The three liquids result in hydrophilic angles ranging from similar profiles to quite different ones. The opaque ink droplet results in a high-contrast image from which segmentation can be automated, while the translucent oil droplet has less internal contrast and it is advantageous under the manual selection mode. The fact that segmentation can be performed for liquids in the transparent (water), translucent (oil), and opaque (ink) cases demonstrates the wide applicability of the segmentation pipeline

C. Validation Against Literature

The reported contact angle ranges for the liquid–substrate couples considered in this work are collected in Table III. Our measured results are within or very close to the literature values, which confirms the feasibility of the system

Table 3. Comparison with Literature values

Liquid – Substrate	Measured θ (°)	Reported Range (°)	Reference
Water – Stainless Steel (as-received)	70.18	70-90	[10]
Water – Thermoplastic Polyurethane	68.18	65-85	[8]
Water – Cellulosic Surface (foam board)	61.24	50-75	[12]

The values obtained for water on stainless steel and TPU comfortably lie within the reported intervals, providing an independent verification of the accuracy of our method. It is well known that as-received stainless-steel surfaces exhibit variable contact angles in response to different storage environments and due to the influence of surface roughness and adsorbed organic films [10] which agrees with our measured contact angle of 70.18° at the lower limit of the reported values.

7. Conclusion

A low-cost contact angle measurement platform was demonstrated based on image processing and static sessile drop method in this paper. The system integrates motorized liquid-dispensing, image capture, and analysis through a single graphical user interface. Experimental results for five liquid–substrate pairs, including water on stainless steel (70.18°), and thermoplastic polyurethane (68.18°) matched values from literature, and a mean left–right angle deviation of 3.43° corroborates the internal consistency of the measurement procedure. The system exemplifies how one can develop affordable, software-controlled instruments with measurement quality adequate for teaching and exploratory research.

In the future, the system will be extended to dynamic contact angle measurement (advancing and receding angles), a complementary mobile application interface will be developed, uniformity of illumination (related to enhance edges contrast) will be further improved, also including auto-sampling and precision enhancement based on feedback on the dispensing subsystem.

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